

Changes in energy and livestock systems largely explain the forest transition in Austria (1830–1910)

Simone Gingrich^{a,*}, Christian Lauk^a, Fridolin Krausmann^a, Karl-Heinz Erb^a, Julia Le Noë^{a,b}

^a University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, Institute of Social Ecology, Schottenfeldgasse 29, 1070 Vienna, Austria

^b Geology Laboratory, École Normale Supérieure, Paris Sciences and Letters University, 75005, France

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ABSTRACT

Achieving a global forest transition, that is a shift from deforestation to reforestation, is important for climate-change mitigation. Forest transitions are enabled by socioecological processes, including land displacement, agricultural intensification and woodfuel substitution for other energy, but their respective contributions remain poorly understood. Here, by means of a scenario approach we quantify the importance of enabling conditions of the forest transition in Austria between 1830 and 1910 and their overall emissions implications, including the forest carbon sink potential in the hypothetical absence of wood use. We combine historical databases on land use, biomass production and energy use and an empirical dynamic forest growth model to develop five hypothetical counterfactual scenarios. The scenarios assume food and energy consumption in the absence of woodfuel substitution, food imports and three variations of agricultural intensification and assess effects on forest change and carbon balances. We find that the absence of any of the enabling conditions would have completely depleted forest biomass by 1910. Livestock efficiency gains and woodfuel substitution, two rarely discussed drivers of forest change, were equally important as yield increase and land displacement. The cumulative forest sink potential in the absence of any wood extraction throughout the period was found to be about twice the forest carbon stock in 1830. All counterfactual scenarios led to increasing overall emissions, “no woodfuel substitution” being closest to the historical trend. Our work lays the ground for a new typology of forest transitions according to the socioecological processes that enable them.

1. Introduction

Halting global deforestation is a major sustainability challenge, in particular in the context of mitigating global climate change (Bastin et al., 2019; IPCC, 2019a; Pan et al., 2011). While global net-deforestation is still ongoing, mostly due to tropical deforestation (Baccini et al., 2017), an increasing number of industrialized and industrializing countries are experiencing forest recovery (Kauppi et al., 2018; Keenan et al., 2015). The long-term national-level shift from deforestation to reforestation has been described as „forest transition“ (Mather, 1992; Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011), characterized by forest area expansion and/or vegetation thickening, i.e. increasing biomass per unit forest area (Kauppi et al., 2006; Köhl et al., 2015).

Understanding the processes that enable forest transitions is crucial for informing effective forest conservation policies towards climate-change mitigation. According to their major socio-economic and political drivers (Rudel et al., 2005), five pathways of forest transitions have

been discerned, namely economic development, globalization, state forest policy, forest scarcity and smallholder tree-based land use intensification (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2010). This categorization has inspired empirical and conceptual analyses of the political (Andoh and Lee, 2018; Riggs et al., 2018) and economic (Barbier et al., 2010; Youn et al., 2016) factors enabling forest transitions. However, these conceptualizations fail to explicitly address the specific biophysical enabling conditions of forest recovery. Given that forest transitions are generally observed in the course of industrialization (Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011; Rudel et al., 2020), periods characterized by significant increases in population, affluence and resource use (Kovanda and Hak, 2011; Krausmann et al., 2011), there must be processes relieving pressure from forests while at the same time enabling growing production and consumption.

The research field of social ecology, investigating the relationships between societies and their natural environments (Haberl et al., 2016), offers explanatory approaches to this issue. Conceptualized as

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: simone.gingrich@boku.ac.at (S. Gingrich).

“socio-ecological transition” (Fischer-Kowalski and Haberl, 2007; Krausmann et al., 2008), social ecology views industrialization as a process during which the increasing use of fossil fuels changes the connection of land and energy use by increasingly substituting bio-energy and subsidizing agricultural production, while causing new ecological problems such as global climate change. Forest transitions have, from this perspective, been described as side-effects of industrialization (Erb et al., 2008; Gingrich et al., 2016). In a recent proposal for socio-ecological analyses of forest transitions, three major biophysical processes relieving forests from pressure have been identified (Gingrich et al., 2019): (1) the substitution of other energy sources for woodfuel, (2) the displacement of land through biomass imports, and (3) the intensification of agriculture, resulting in land-sparing effects.

The effects of displacing biomass production to other countries are studied extensively in the context of forest transitions (Friis and Nielsen, 2019; Meyfroidt et al., 2013). National-level reforestation today is linked to wood extraction or deforestation abroad in many national cases (Jadin et al., 2016a; Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2009) and even at the global scale (Kastner et al., 2011; Pendrill et al., 2019). Agricultural intensification, while acknowledged as an important driver of forest transitions (Mather and Needle, 1998), is less commonly quantitatively assessed (Jadin et al., 2016b; García et al., 2020). The focus here tends to be on the spatial reconfiguration of agricultural land towards more suitable areas („agricultural adjustment to land quality“, (Mather and Needle, 1998)), rather than the systemic effect of increasing land and livestock productivity on forest expansion (Burney et al., 2010). The effect of woodfuel substitution on forest transitions, finally, has even less frequently been investigated empirically (exceptions are e.g. Erb et al., 2008; Myllyntaus and Mattila, 2002). While these three forest relief processes are, to diverging degrees, studied in forest transitions research, no integrated analysis of their contributions to forest change has been conducted. Such analyses are of particular importance in the context of land-based climate-change mitigation, because they may result in emissions counteracting the carbon (C) sink of forest transitions (Scheidt, 2018).

Here we aim at filling this research gap by assessing the relative contributions of different forest relief processes to the forest transition in Austria in 1830–1910, and quantifying their respective GHG implications. We adopt a counterfactual approach to investigate, under *ceteris paribus* conditions, trends in forest area and forest biomass, as well as overall greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, in the hypothetical absence of (1) woodfuel substitution, (2) land displacement and (3) variations of agricultural intensification, (a) yield increase, (b) livestock efficiency increase and (c) the combination of both.

Austria represents a promising case, because it combines high and robust data availability with an interesting historical trajectory with no obvious single explanation for the forest transition: forest recovery occurred before the large-scale industrialization of agriculture (Gingrich and Krausmann, 2018), and Austria, as part of the Habsburg Monarchy, was less involved in international trade than other European countries (Bairoch, 1973). On the other hand, population growth and industrialization increased the demand for food and energy (Sieferle et al., 2006). Additionally, the Austrian forest transition was, in contrast to other cases (Le Noë et al., 2020a; Magerl et al., 2019), the result of both forest area expansion and vegetation thickening (Gingrich et al., 2007). With our integrated socio-ecological analysis of the biophysical factors enabling the forest transition in the case of Austria and their GHG implications, we aim at engaging a dialogue between the existing conceptual frameworks for understanding forest transitions (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2010; Rudel et al., 2005) and quantitative assessments of long-term forest C sinks (Kauppi et al., 2006; Köhl et al., 2015; Le Noë et al., 2020a; Magerl et al., 2019).

2. Methods and data

For Austria during the period of the forest transition (1830–1910),

our analysis presents observed dynamics of (1) forest area and forest biomass density (i.e., forest biomass per unit area), as well as the associated forest C balances, and (2) the GHG emissions from agriculture and energy, as well as the sink in harvested wood products. We compare these empirical findings to assessments of hypothetical forest change and emissions in five counterfactual scenarios. Each counterfactual scenario represents the absence of one specific forest relief process, while parameters of food and energy consumption are kept constant. The underlying hypothesis is that shifts in the way of producing food and generating energy enabled an increase in food and energy consumption and a simultaneous forest recovery (Gingrich et al., 2019). We do not aim at portraying plausible alternative historical pathways, but at assessing the effect of socio-ecological processes on the forest transition, as well as on overall GHG emissions.

The study period 1830–1910 covers an early stage of Austria’s long-term forest recovery and the earliest period of regular and comparable statistical records. While the turning point of forest cover may even lie before 1830, analyzing this period enables portraying long-term trends of resource use and their impact on forest change during the initial, coal-based period of industrialization. In addition, the eighty-year perspective allows for studying the effect of different temporal dynamics in resource use and forest change (e.g., slow vs. rapid change, saturation effects).

2.1. Datasets on trends in forest change, agricultural and energy emissions, 1830–1910

We built on existing datasets on forest and agricultural change, as well as food and energy consumption on the territory matching current Austria in the period 1830–1910 (e.g. Erb et al., 2008; Gingrich et al., 2016; Krausmann, 2001a) to produce (1) a consistent estimate of change in forest area and forest aboveground plus belowground biomass and the resulting C fluxes, and (2) estimates of GHG emissions from agricultural activities and energy use, as well as C fluxes associated to harvested wood products.

Forest biomass data were derived from a previous assessment (Gingrich et al., 2007) that defined biomass stocks in different land-use categories for 1830, 1880 and 1910, discerning aboveground and belowground biomass stocks in forests. Forest area extent is based on contemporary agricultural statistics which were originally compiled by Krausmann (2001b). The assessment of forest biomass density in 1830 and 1880 relies on primary sources, i.e. the Franciscan Cadastre (Moritsch, 1972) and Schindler (1889, 1885), reporting standing timber volume or tree species composition, rotation period and harvest. Biomass expansion factors were applied to derive total biomass from timber volumes (for details, see Gingrich et al., 2007). For 1910, only data on forest area is available, but not on forest biomass density. In the absence of better information, we thus used a linear interpolation of forest biomass density between 1880 and 1960 when a national assessment of Austria’s forest C stocks is available (Weiss et al., 2000).

Data on forest production was also derived from previous work, estimating total wood extraction annually (Krausmann, 2001b), differentiating deciduous and coniferous wood extraction (Erb et al., 2008), as well as use as woodfuel or timber (Gingrich et al., 2016). We quantified the C source from (or sink in) harvested wood products based on information on timber use (annual inflows to C stocks in harvested wood products), and assumptions on lifecycles of industrial roundwood and paper (annual outflows). The difference of inflows and outflows was considered the net flux (for details, see Gingrich et al., 2016).

Information on forest area, forest biomass and wood extraction was used to calibrate the CRAFT model (“CaRbon Accumulation in ForesTs”) that computes forest biomass stocks in deciduous and coniferous forests as a function of area and wood extraction (Le Noë et al., 2020a). The model applies a parabolic function linking annual net primary productivity NPP [$\text{tC/ha}\cdot\text{yr}$] to forest biomass stocks B [tC/ha], by establishing the annual growth rate r [yr^{-1}] and a hypothetical carrying capacity K

[tC/ha] for coniferous and deciduous forests separately, according to the formula $NPP = r \cdot B \cdot (1 - B/K)$.

In order to quantify biomass stock values in succeeding years, CRAFT considers annual fluxes induced by harvest, harvest losses, natural mortality, and area change (Le Noë et al., 2020a). The parameters r and K were derived from country-specific forest yield tables (Marschall, 1975), providing net annual increment (i.e., the average annual increase in timber stocks due to tree growth) for different tree species in different site productivity classes. We optimized the distribution of productivity classes to derive r and K values for the most representative tree species in order to generate forest biomass trends consistent with the empirical data set described above. This way, we established constant r values of 0.08 for deciduous and 0.07 for coniferous forests, and K values of 320 and 374 for deciduous and coniferous forests respectively, similar to the ones estimated for French forests (Le Noë et al., 2020a). The reproduction of forest biomass trends through the CRAFT model was used as an input for the counterfactual scenarios.

We assessed emissions from forest change in two complementary ways, using different benchmarks: Firstly, following IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2019b), we quantified changes in biomass stocks relative to the previous year (“stock-change method”). We refer to these as “emissions” or “sinks” when forest biomass stocks decline or increase respectively. Secondly, we investigated the opportunity costs of forest use, or the “sink foregone” due to wood extraction (Gerber et al., 2013; Marques et al., 2019). The “sink foregone” is defined as the difference between the actual C balance of a managed terrestrial ecosystem and the sink that would materialize due to natural succession in the hypothetical absence of any human intervention. Previous assessments (e.g. Marques et al., 2019) quantified the sink foregone in forests as the amount of harvested wood in each year, because it would otherwise be left standing in the forest. CRAFT however enabled us to take long-term temporal dynamics of forest biomass saturation into account: We calculated a forest change scenario in which forest areas defined in the actual trend recover throughout the period in the hypothetical absence of wood harvest, considering also mortality and saturation effects. The sink foregone was then calculated as the difference between the potential C sink in a particular year and the observed C stock change of that year. The net sink in the absence of wood harvest was considered as the forest sink potential.

We estimated, for the first time, agricultural GHG emissions for Austria 1830–1910, including N_2O and CH_4 emissions from enteric fermentation, manure management, manure deposited on pastures and crop residues (for a detailed description, see Supplementary Information S1). To build this dataset, we used input data on agricultural practices for biomass and livestock production and consumption, relying on agricultural statistics at approximately decadal resolution which were compiled in previous studies (Gingrich and Krausmann, 2018; Krausmann, 2001b; Sieferle et al., 2006). We followed IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2019b) to estimate N_2O and CH_4 emissions from manure management and the method described in the GLEAM model (FAO, 2017) for CH_4 emissions from enteric fermentation. N_2O emissions were calculated as product of N contained in manure and crop residues, and coefficients such as N_2O emission factors. CH_4 emissions from manure management were calculated from volatile solid excretion, shares of manure management systems, emission factors for each manure management system and other standard coefficients. CH_4 emissions from enteric fermentation were derived from feed intake and digestibilities. Nitrogen and volatile solid excretion, required for the calculation of N_2O emissions and CH_4 emissions from manure, were calculated from feed intake, feed digestibilities and output of livestock products. N_2O and CH_4 emissions were converted into CO_2 equivalents, using factors for global warming potential with climate C feedbacks (CH_4 34, N_2O 298, (Myrhe et al., 2014)).

Information on food consumption was derived from a previous calculation building on contemporary agricultural statistics and assumptions on per-capita food demand (Krausmann, 2004). Similarly,

data on energy use and resulting emissions were taken from a previous assessment based on estimates of amount and composition of coal consumption, distinguishing brown coal and hard coal (Erb et al., 2008).

We established GHG budgets in CO_2 equivalents, including emissions (or sinks) from forest change, agricultural activities, fossil energy use and harvested wood products.

2.2. Counterfactual scenarios

We investigated three major forest relief processes in five counterfactual scenarios (CS), addressing two interrelated research questions:

- (1) How would the hypothetical absence of a specific forest relief process have affected the Austrian forest transition in terms of forest biomass stocks, forest area and forest biomass density?
- (2) What were the overall GHG effects of each CS as compared to the actually observed trend, considering not only forest change but also emissions from energy and agriculture, as well as harvested wood products?

All CS assume the consumption of food and energy to follow the observed historical trajectory, while each CS isolates the effect of a particular forest relief process (Table 1) on forest area, forest biomass density and forest biomass stocks, as well as on overall GHG emissions. All CS start in the year 1830 and quantify the development that would have occurred in the absence of the respective process, keeping all other parameters unaltered.

We chose simple, transparent and conservative model assumptions in order to isolate the minimum effect of the different forest relief processes. Important choices on system boundaries include:

- Following a territory-based approach (Peters, 2008), GHG fluxes related to agricultural activities or land cover change outside the domestic territory were not considered in any of the scenarios.

Table 1
Rationales of the five counterfactual scenarios.

Scenario	Assumption	Impact on forests, causing additional emissions	Impact on other emissions
CS1: no woodfuel substitution	All technical energy consumption is provided by wood	No effect on forest area Increase in wood harvest pressure	Change in energy emissions
CS2: no land displacement	Net food deficit is produced within the domestic territory at average emissions intensities, thus domestic land requirement for food production increases	Reduction of forest area Increase in wood harvest pressure	Change in agricultural emissions
CS3a: no yield increase	Agricultural yields remain constant at the level of 1830, thus land requirement for agricultural production increases	Reduction of forest area Increase in wood harvest pressure	No effect on agricultural emissions
CS3b: no feed conversion efficiency increase	Ratio between animal production and feed input remains constant at the level of 1830, thus land requirement for feed production increases	Reduction of forest area Increase in wood harvest pressure	Change in agricultural emissions
CS3c: no agricultural intensification	Sum of CF 3a and CF3b	Reduction of forest area Increase in wood harvest pressure	Change in agricultural emissions

- We limit the analysis to C stocks in biomass only, omitting change in soil organic C (SOC). While SOC represents a C pool larger than biomass (Scharlemann et al., 2014), it changes at a slower pace than biomass (Gingrich et al., 2007), and data uncertainty is higher (Le Noë et al., 2020a).
- In cases of complete forest depletion, we developed modelling assumptions (see Supporting Information S2) resulting in (1) lower sinks in (or even emissions from) harvested wood products in case of timber shortage, and (2) higher emissions from coal when woodfuel demand could not be met.

2.2.1. Counterfactual Scenario 1: No woodfuel substitution

In CS1, „no woodfuel substitution“, we assessed how forest biomass stocks would have developed if all technical energy consumed in the form of coal (the only other major technical energy source in the period) had been derived from domestic forests as woodfuel, in addition to the woodfuel actually used. We assumed no change in forest area compared to the actual trend, but increased wood harvest pressure resulting in a decline of forest biomass density.

To quantify the additional woodfuel requirement, we converted the actual annual consumption of coal (PJ/yr) into a hypothetical volume of fuelwood (tC/yr), taking into account the lower energy content of wood compared to coal (BMWA, 1990). We added this additional woodfuel to the actual wood extraction. By exchanging values of wood extraction in the CRAFT model, we dynamically assessed the change in forest biomass as a result of the higher level of harvest pressure.

2.2.2. Counterfactual Scenario 2: No land displacement

In CS2, we assessed trajectories in forest C and agricultural emissions in the hypothetical absence of agricultural biomass imports. Assuming no change in biomass consumption, all biomass demand in this scenario was assumed to be covered by domestic production.

Given that the territory under investigation was not an independent state at the time, no statistical reports on biomass imports are available. Economic history reports that food was traded in substantial quantities from the Hungarian part to the Western provinces of the Habsburg Monarchy, particularly to Vienna (Berend and Ranki, 1980; Komlos, 1983). Regarding the trade of wood, there is evidence for both, imports and exports in 19th century Austria: In 1868, Vienna reportedly derived 24% of the wood used in the city via the Danube from outside the Austrian territory, i.e. the German province Bavaria (K.K. Statistische Central-Commission, 1870). Wessely (1867) on the other hand portrays the North-Western provinces of the Habsburg Monarchy as important export regions of wood. In the absence of trade data and in order to develop a transparent and conservative estimate, we assumed no net land displacement by wood trade in CS2. Thus, only the land displacement through food imports was accounted for.

CS2 uses the difference between domestic food production and domestic food demand in GJ nutritional value (Krausmann, 2004) as a proxy for displaced biomass production. To assess the impact of land displacement on domestic emissions, we assumed agricultural land and agricultural emissions to increase according to the share of the food deficit in the domestic food production in the respective year. Increases in agricultural land were then considered as reductions in forest area, resulting in a decline in forest biomass due to both reduction of forest area and increased harvest pressure on the remaining forest. The absence of imports creates differences in forest area already in 1830. In order to create plausible starting conditions, we assumed forest biomass density in 1830 to equal actual forest biomass density in that year. Therefore, CS2 starts from a lower total biomass stock than the other CS. Following the rationale of territorial accounting, we did not account for the potential impact of land displacement on reforestation abroad.

It can be assumed that agricultural land was, at each point in time, concentrated on favourable soils, and that any additional agricultural land demand would have required taking less favourable soils into

production. Due to lack of data, we performed a sensitivity analysis to assess the effect of lower productivity on additional agricultural land. To this end, we assumed that average yields on “additional agricultural land” were 80% of actual yields in each year, corresponding to the ratio between the wheat yield in the lowest yielding province and in the Austrian average in 1830 (Sandgruber, 1978). In the sensitivity analysis, we quantified the effect of such reduced yields on additional agricultural land demand, and compared the results to our original assessment.

2.2.3. Counterfactual Scenarios 3a, 3b and 3c: No agricultural intensification

Three variations of CS in the absence of agricultural intensification were developed to investigate forest change under differing “no agricultural intensification” assumptions. These CS result in an increased agricultural land demand and, in part, in increased agricultural emissions.

CS3a investigates the effect of agricultural yield increase on forest change by assuming constant yields on agricultural land throughout the period. All increase in crop production, grazing and hay production was instead assumed to stem from agricultural expansion. The increased agricultural land was translated into a decline in forest area and, at the same levels of wood extraction as in the actual trend, into higher wood harvest pressure. Agricultural emissions are the same as in the observed trend, as agricultural emissions are not directly affected by changing yields, but only by livestock and soil management.

CS3b assesses how efficiency gains in the livestock system affected land requirements for feed production, as well as agricultural emissions from livestock caused by the changes in feed demand. To that end, the ratio of feed intake per unit final animal product (meat and milk for ruminants, meat and eggs for monogastrics) was assumed to remain constant throughout the period, resulting in higher feed demand than in the actual trend, thus increasing land requirement for feed production. Again, the increased demand for agricultural land was translated into a decrease of forest area and higher wood harvest pressure per unit forest land. In addition, the increased feed intake results in higher agricultural emissions from enteric fermentation and manure production.

Finally, CS3c assumes neither yield increases nor livestock efficiency gains. For all three CS3 scenarios, we conducted sensitivity analyses in the same way as for CS2, investigating the effect of yield reductions by 20% on additional agricultural land.

3. Results

3.1. Observed trends of forest change and food and energy use in Austria (1830–1910)

The forest transition in Austria was characterized by combined increases in forest area and forest biomass density (Gingrich et al., 2007, Fig. 1a). Forest area accounted for 40% of the territory in 1910 (31,700 km²), and was 3% above the level of 1830 (30,700 km²). Forest biomass density grew from 6.2 kgC/m² in 1830–7.3 kgC/m² in 1910 (17% increase) according to the empirical assessment, and to 7.1 kgC/m² (14% increase) according to the CRAFT model simulation.

Trends in forest biomass density were the result of significant and continuous harvest interventions, as demonstrated by the strong increase in the potential biomass density (Fig. 1): In the hypothetical absence of wood extraction, forest biomass density would have increased steeply in the first half of the period, and saturated towards the end of our investigation period. The maximum estimated value of 17.4 kgC/m² in 1910 established here through the CRAFT simulation is slightly higher than in previous assessments of potential biomass stocks in Austria (Gingrich et al., 2007 estimate 15.6 kg/m²), which relied on reports from ecological site measurements as input data, rather than forest yield tables (Erb, 2004).

The net change in forest biomass was the result of annual gross gains and losses in forest C stocks (Fig. 1b). Until c. 1870, extraction of

Fig. 1. Forest change in Austria, 1830–1910. (a) Forest area, actual forest biomass density as observed in empirical data and reproduced by the CRAFT model, and potential biomass density in the absence of wood extraction. (b) Annual forest C fluxes, positive values indicating C emissions to the atmosphere, negative values indicating terrestrial C sinks. Forest sink potential denotes the annual C flux in the absence of any wood extraction. Forest sink foregone denotes the sink lost each year through wood extraction, calculated as “net flux forest change” minus “forest sink potential”.

woodfuel dominated over timber extraction, and total extraction was roughly equal to annual biomass regrowth at 4 MtC/yr. Therefore, the net sink (“net flux forest change” in Fig. 1b) in forest biomass was negligible. From 1870–1910, wood extraction declined because of a strong reduction in woodfuel harvest, despite slight increases in timber harvest. Annual forest biomass regrowth increasingly exceeded extraction and the annual net sink reached 1.7 MtC/yr in the early 20th century.

The difference between actual stock change and the annual forest sink potential reveals the annual sink foregone over the period. In 1830–1870, the sink foregone was larger than annual biomass extraction (up to 115% of annual extraction, including losses), ranging between 5 and 6 MtC/yr. After 1870, the declining wood extraction and resulting actual net forest sink coincided with the hypothetical saturation of potential annual forest growth. The annual sink foregone declined to 0.3 MtC/yr, or only 8% of annual wood extraction by 1910 (Fig. 1b). At this point however, the total potential biomass density in forests would have

been ~3 times the actual density due to natural regeneration resulting in average ageing of trees (Fig. 1a).

The gradual regeneration of Austrian forests in the 19th century is in opposition to more rapid changes in food consumption and energy use (Fig. 2a). Food demand, driven by population growth, increased by 84% in the course of the period. Food production almost kept pace, rising by 70%, with fluctuations mostly resulting from weather-dependent variations in crop yields. Technical energy use, comprising primary energy of woodfuel and coal, grew by a factor 2.7 between 1830 and 1910.

The increase in food production (Fig. 2a) did not translate into an equal increase of agricultural emissions (Fig. 2b): The amount of food produced per ton of GHG emissions in CO₂ equivalents was roughly stable between 1830 and 1880 (2.7–2.9 GJ nutritional value (NV)) and grew to 4.3 GJ NV by 1910. This relative decoupling of food production from agricultural emissions was the effect of two major trends: First, feed conversion efficiencies (feed input per unit of animal product) improved considerably over the period for ruminants, horses and

Fig. 2. Changes in processes relieving forests from pressure and their emissions effects in Austria, 1830–1910. (a) changes in energy use, food production and food consumption; net GHG emissions from (b) agriculture and (c) energy use. (d) GHG budget from forest change, harvested wood products, agriculture, and energy, as sum of emissions and actual sinks. Woodfuel combustion is not considered here as part of energy, but as forest stock change.

monogastrics alike. For ruminants and horses, each kg dry matter of output (milk and carcass) required 26 kg dry matter (DM) of feed inputs in 1830, while this ratio declined to 17 in 1910. For monogastrics, this input/output-ratio decreased from 17 in 1830 to 6 in 1910. These values are comparable to those of current traditional livestock systems (Bouwman et al., 2005; Herrero et al., 2013; TOMAK, 2017). For ruminants, which are important drivers of CH₄ emissions, this trend was particularly pronounced in the period 1890–1910. As agricultural GHG emissions are strongly linked to feed inputs, especially for ruminants, this resulted in a decrease of GHG emissions relative to food production. Second, the share of products from monogastrics (mainly pork) in total animal product output increased from 5% in 1830 to 17% in 1910. As monogastric products have lower GHG emission intensities than ruminant products, mainly due to CH₄ from ruminant enteric fermentation, this shift further decoupled GHG emissions from food production.

Energy use resulted in more than a doubling of energy-related CO₂ emissions from 12 MtCO₂/yr in 1830 to 28 MtCO₂/yr in 1910. The increase in CO₂ emissions, though steep, was less than the increase in energy use (Fig. 2a), because of the shift from woodfuel to coal with a higher energy density. Energy efficiency (unit energy used per unit energy-related CO₂ emissions) slightly increased from 9.0 GJ/tCO₂ in 1830 to 10.1 GJ/tCO₂ in 1910. In contrast, the amount of total (coal plus woodfuel) energy provided per unit of fossil energy emissions strongly declined from over 2000 GJ/tCO₂ at the beginning to 12 GJ/tCO₂ at the end of the period, thus indicating a shift from a biotic solar-based to a fossil-based energy system (Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2014).

A compilation of emissions from forest change, harvested wood products (if negative, these are sinks), coal use and agricultural activities, all expressed in CO₂ equivalents, is displayed in Fig. 2d. The major dynamic was a strong increase in CO₂ emissions from coal use since the mid-19th century, which exceeded agricultural emissions in 1880 and grew to a value four times the level of agricultural emissions by 1910. These emissions were partially counteracted by increasing sinks in forests and in harvested wood products, compensating for gross emissions from coal and agriculture in 1910 by 21% and 9% respectively.

3.2. The biophysical enabling conditions of the forest transition in Austria

Our results reveal that the forest transition in Austria was the combined result of several biophysical enabling conditions. The assessment of five counterfactual scenarios shows that the absence of any of the identified forest relief processes would have not only reversed the forest transition in Austria in the observed time period, but would have even resulted in a complete depletion of forest biomass before the end of the observation period (Fig. 3a).

Agricultural intensification (CS3c), i.e. the combination of yield increase and livestock efficiency increase, was the most important factor impacting forest change, in line with assessments of the impact of recent agricultural intensification on forest land (Burney et al., 2010; Ewers et al., 2009; Jadin et al., 2016b). In the absence of agricultural intensification, forest biomass stocks would have been depleted in 1886. But also in all other CS, forest biomass would have been depleted before the end of the observation period (between 1906 and 1910). Specifically, it is notable that shifts in livestock (CS3b) and energy (CS1) systems were of similar importance as the other enabling conditions of forest transitions which have traditionally been in research focus, i.e. yield improvements (CS3a) and land displacement (CS2).

The changes in forest biomass stock result from the combined impacts of forest area change (Fig. 3b) and increasing wood harvest pressure, leading to reduced forest biomass density (Fig. 3c). Through our modelling assumptions, CS1 (“no woodfuel substitution”) does not assume any impact on forest area, while all other scenarios do. CS3c (“no agricultural intensification”) results in a complete loss of forest area by 1907, while the other scenarios lead to forest area reductions by 47% (CS3b), 39% (CS3a), and 29% (CS2) compared to the actual forest area in 1910.

Forest biomass density declined to zero before the end of the scenario period in all counterfactual scenarios. The fact that forest biomass is more affected than forest area in all CS is due to the scenario design, where forest area reduction also affects forest biomass density due to increased harvest pressure, while the reverse is not true. The strong impact on biomass density displays the diverging dynamics of forest area and biomass, and underlines the importance of considering both, C

Fig. 3. Forest change in the actual trend (model and data) and in five counterfactual scenarios, Austria 1830–1910. Trends in (a) forest biomass stock, (b) forest area and (c) forest biomass density in the actual and counterfactual scenarios CS1 “no woodfuel substitution”, CS2 “no land displacement”, CS3a “no yield increase”, CS3b “no livestock efficiency increase”, and CS3c “no agricultural intensification”. Forest biomass stock is the product of forest area and biomass density, and is zero if either of the two is zero. (d) Cumulative net forest C fluxes (1830–1910) in the actual trend and the CS: cumulative emissions from stock change, sink foregone and forest sink potential.

density and area, when investigating forest transitions (Kauppi et al., 2006).

The comparison between actual forest C trends and the forest sink potential informs about the foregone C sink in forests (Fig. 3d). Given that the forest sink potential over the time period amounted to a total of -361 MtC, the cumulative observed C sink (-33 MtC) appears only as a small realization of this potential, while the sink foregone (i.e., the difference of actual fluxes and potential sink) remained high (328 MtC). The counterfactual scenarios, by depleting forest biomass towards zero, resulted in net emissions from forests equivalent to the biomass stock at the starting point (191 MtC for CS 1 and CS 3 a, b and c, and 173 MtC for CS2 which started at a lower level in 1830). While the actual emissions differed in direction between the observed trend and the CS, the sink foregone shows the same signal, ranging from 328 MtC (actual trend) to 534 (CS2) and 552 MtC (CS1, 3a, b and c). The observed forest changes thus differed more from the forest sink potential than from the counterfactual scenarios. This highlights that the observed forest transition was only a partial recovery process.

3.3. The overall GHG effects of diverging ways to provide food and energy

The changes in forest biomass were related to changes in agriculture and the energy system. The overall GHG effects of diverging ways to provide food and energy, considering also activity-based emissions from agriculture and energy use, are displayed in Fig. 4.

Cumulative agricultural emissions, which amounted to 491 MtCO_{2e} in the actual trend, increased to 537 MtCO_{2e} or 109% of the actual trend (CS2) and 569 MtCO_{2e} or 116% (CS3b and c) in those counterfactuals with altered agricultural emissions. These higher emissions resulted from higher livestock emissions, due to either more livestock production (CS2) or less efficient feed conversion rates and therefore higher feed intake (CS3b and c). Agricultural intensification was thus associated to savings in GHG emissions, similar to efficiency gains documented at the global level in the 20th century (Bennetzen et al., 2016; Hong et al., 2021).

Total emissions from energy use (actual cumulative total: 1398 MtCO_{2e}) differed less among the scenarios than agricultural emissions, being only affected by the diverging relative contribution of woodfuel or coal (Fig. 4a). The highest value was reached in CS1 (105% of actual), due to the highest fraction of woodfuel consumption, and the lowest in CS3c (99%), where woodfuel consumption was lowest, because in this CS forest depletion reduced woodfuel availability most.

Fig. 4b displays that the GHG effect of forest change in the CS outweighs the differences in activity-based emissions. The values here refer to forest emissions (i.e. cumulative stock change), and do not additionally account for emissions from woodfuel combustion, because emissions from wood use are already considered in net forest biomass change. The cumulative emissions were higher in all CS than in the actual trend, mostly resulting from relatively higher emissions from forest change. In addition, the lower wood availability due to forest

depletion resulted in declining sinks in harvested wood products compared to the actual fluxes (CS1, 2, 3a and 3b), or even net emissions from harvested wood products (CS3c). In CS1, net cumulative emissions exceeded actual cumulative emissions by 47%. In CS2, CS3a, CS3b and CS3c cumulative emissions exceed the actual emissions by a factor 2 (CS2) to 2.24 (CS3c), because in these scenarios, in addition to forest depletion and reduced sinks in harvested wood products, emissions from coal use were higher than in the actual total. The cumulative forest sink potential throughout the period was higher than the total cumulative activity-based emissions (i.e., agriculture plus energy) in all scenarios.

The difference in overall emissions among CS indicates that shifts in the energy system had an important impact on overall GHG emissions. In combination with the finding that CS1 “no woodfuel substitution” would have depleted forest biomass before the end of the observation period, this points to the crucial importance of considering fuel shifts in research on the climate-change mitigation effect of reforestation (Gingrich et al., 2019; Scheidel, 2018).

4. Discussion

The present study investigates the relative contribution of different enabling conditions to the forest transition and the resulting GHG impacts in the territory of present-day Austria during 1830–1910. From a socio-ecological perspective, we scrutinize the effects of biophysical enabling processes, including woodfuel substitution, land displacement and agricultural intensification (discerning yield increase, livestock efficiency increase, and the combination of both). We show that two enabling conditions rarely considered in forest transitions research, efficiency increase in livestock production and shifts in the energy system, affected forest change similar in extent as two more commonly discussed conditions, yield increase and land displacement.

4.1. Limitations

The results of our counterfactual analysis are based on several simplifying assumptions. The scenarios are hypothetical in nature and aim at scrutinizing the weight of individual forest relief processes. They do not consider complex technical or economic processes and dynamic feedbacks which might have taken place in those hypothetical cases (Evenson and Gollin, 2003; Stevenson et al., 2013).

Some potentially important additional forest management activities contributing to forest thickening (i.e. increase of forest biomass density) were omitted in our assessment, because our data and methods did not allow for including them. One of them is the reduction of agricultural side uses such as forest grazing and litter extraction in 19th century forest management (Gimmi and Buergi, 2007; Henttonen et al., 2019; McGrath et al., 2015; Tasser et al., 2007). Similarly, the possible additional long-term effect of professional forest management (Thom et al., 2018) was not explicitly considered either. Beyond the exclusion of livestock grazing and litter extraction, this comprises the protection of

Fig. 4. Emissions effects of counterfactual scenarios. (a) Activity-based emissions from agriculture and energy use; (b) Total cumulative emissions in the actual and counterfactual scenarios, 1830–1910 (forest change refers to forest emissions as stock difference, and includes the effect of woodfuel use), and cumulative forest sink potential (FSP) in the absence of any wood extraction; CS1 “no woodfuel substitution”, CS2 “no land displacement”, CS3a “no yield increase”, CS3b “no livestock efficiency increase”, and CS3c “no agricultural intensification”.

young trees, the selection of tree species, the thinning of forest stands, etc., to optimize tree growth. While the effect of agricultural side uses is potentially significant (Erb et al., 2013; Niedertscheider et al., 2017), we consider management effects to be less significant than the forest relief processes investigated. The fact that the CRAFT model produced optimal results at constant parameters of tree growth (r and K) implies stable forest growth conditions throughout the period, ruling out significant improvement of tree growth from reduced degradation or improved management.

Additional limitations result from the fact that, due to data scarcity, we could not consider differences in soil quality on land productivity and effects on average yields or emissions. A sensitivity assessment, quantifying the potential impact of lower land productivity on additional agricultural land requirements for agricultural expansion in CS2, 3a, 3b and 3c reveals that our approach yields conservative results. Under the assumption of 20% lower yields on additional agricultural land, forest biomass stocks would have been depleted 5 (CS 3b), 6 (CS3c) or 7 (CS2 and CS3a) years before the best estimate. This earlier depletion resulted in reduced cumulative forest biomass stocks over the period (i. e., the sum of biomass stocks in each year) by 15% (CS3c), 13% (CS3b), 12% (CS2) and 10% (CS3a).

The inevitable choice of spatio-temporal system boundaries also impacts results. Forest change is bound to specific temporal dynamics which differ from the trends in energy use or food consumption (compare e.g. Figs. 1b and 2a). In our scenarios, shorter periods of investigation would have failed to show saturation effects of the forest sink potential, or the full depletion of forest biomass (in particular the rapid biomass density decline resulting from overextraction, particularly pronounced in CS1 “no woodfuel substitution”), while longer periods would have increased the energy deficit from woodfuel use after forest depletion. Regarding the spatial scope, the fact that we chose a territorial perspective, excluding emissions from forest change and agricultural activities outside the domestic territory, has important implications. Imports of wood and forest-risk commodities can, for example, result in forest depletion and emissions elsewhere (Kastner et al., 2011; Pendrill et al., 2019), while domestic production might enable reforestation abroad. Consumption-based assessments of the environmental impacts of historical trade relations (Brolin and Kander, 2020; Henriques and Warde, 2018; Le Noë et al., 2020b) will need to be extended by a perspective on land-use based emissions to assess those effects.

4.2. Implications for sustainable forest transitions

Our study provides a new, socio-ecological perspective on forest change, complementing the prevalent focus of previous studies on political, economic (Barbier et al., 2010; Kull, 2017; Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2010) or spatial (Jadin et al., 2016b) dimensions of forest change. A key characteristic of our approach is that it embeds the forest transition in changes of both land and energy use (Gingrich et al., 2019), thus offering a new way of classifying forest transitions according to their major socio-ecological enabling conditions. The case of 19th century Austria, where imports of biomass played a minor role and agricultural intensification was not yet affected by the green revolution, shows that changes in the energy and livestock systems, factors not yet well integrated in forest transitions research, play significant roles for long-term forest change.

Our approach offers important context for the role of reforestation in climate change mitigation today. It informs debates on the climate-change mitigation potential of agricultural intensity (Burney et al., 2010; Havlík et al., 2014), dietary choices (Popp et al., 2010; Stehfest et al., 2009; Theurl et al., 2020), or a shift towards a bioeconomy (Hausknot et al., 2017; Lewandowski, 2015). The finding that agricultural intensification in 19th century Austria was the most important enabling condition of the forest transition, while resulting in declining GHG emissions per unit of agricultural product, implies that it was possible to intensify agriculture and save emissions at the same time.

The increases in feed conversion efficiency were enabled partly by changes in diets, i.e. a shift from ruminant to monogastric animal products, and partly by changes in livestock management practices (Krausmann, 2004; Mazoyer and Roudart, 2006). In terms of GHG emissions, livestock intensification in 19th century Austria had the double benefit of enabling both higher forest biomass stocks by saving land (enabling the forest transition) and lower agricultural emissions per unit of agricultural product. The overall GHG benefit of agricultural intensification due to land savings corroborates similar findings that globally, significant emissions from deforestation were avoided in 1961–2005 because of agricultural intensification (Burney et al., 2010). In contrast to trends in the second half of the 20th century, land savings in 19th century Austria were largely achieved by agro-ecological means, e.g. through new leguminous crops, a shift from grazing to forage, and improved plant nutrient management (Sieferle et al., 2006). The case of early industrializing Austria thus shows that even without the large-scale use of fossil-fuel based and GHG-intensive technologies such as tractors and mineral fertilizers, agricultural intensification combined with shifts in diets resulting in changes in the livestock sector, can significantly contribute to land savings. Our results thus support arguments towards the potential of agroecological intensification for climate-change mitigation (Altieri and Nicholls, 2013).

Our results also point to the importance of linking forest change to energy use in climate-change mitigation strategies (Scheidel, 2018). In contrast to the intensification of agriculture, the shift to fossil energy was the result of access to non-renewable resources. The shift to fossil energy was an important driver of the forest transition in 19th century Austria, and we argue that energy transitions also need to be taken into account in forest conservation strategies today, such as REDD+ (Turnhout et al., 2017). Obviously, current energy transitions involve more renewables than those of the 19th century, but coal represents the highest fraction of global fossil CO₂ emissions today (Friedlingstein et al., 2019), and “non-annex I parties” under the Kyoto Protocol (mostly developing and least developed countries) more than doubled their emissions from coal use between 1990 and 2017 (IEA, 2019). In addition, present-day forest transitions have been shown to coincide with higher emissions from energy consumption, e.g. in Southeast Asia (Pichler et al., 2021). Forest conservation efforts aiming at climate-change mitigation therefore need to explicitly avoid potentially problematic shifts of replacing woodfuel for coal or other fossil energy sources.

The results obtained for CS1 also show that even in an early stage of industrialization, sourcing the growing energy demand from wood would have not only entirely depleted the forest, but would also have created overall emissions higher than in the observed historical trend. This confirms that the climate-change mitigation effect of woodfuel use is not necessarily positive. Afforestation of previously non-forested land may in some contexts serve to provide a limited amount of bioenergy while still conserving ecosystem C sinks (Kalt et al., 2019). However, unsustainably extracting wood to replace high levels of fossil energy use is not a viable climate-change mitigation strategy (Grübler et al., 2018), because it depletes existing terrestrial C pools (Searchinger et al., 2018) and generates energy of higher emissions per unit energy than even coal.

Finally, the analysis of the actual emissions from forest change versus the sink foregone sheds light on the opportunity costs of wood use (Gerber et al., 2013; Ter-Mikaelian et al., 2015). In the case of Austria, the C stocks in forests would have almost tripled over a period of 80 years in the absence of wood extraction after 1830. The forest sink potential over the period of 80 years was larger than the emissions from fossil fuel use and agriculture in the same period, and larger than the biomass stock in forests in 1830. This means that assessing the C-performance of biomass use without taking this opportunity cost into account is prone to misinterpretations. The lack of forest C sequestration needs to be taken into account when comparing the climate-change mitigation performance of biomass to that of other renewable energy sources (DeCicco and Schlesinger, 2018; Griscom et al., 2017;

Holtmark, 2012; Kalt et al., 2020), in particular when assessing short-term effects of different options (Norton et al., 2019).

5. Outlook

The integrated socio-ecological perspective on the forest transition in 19th century Austria demonstrates that forest transitions were the combined effect of several biophysical enabling conditions. In particular, previously-neglected changes in the livestock and energy systems played important roles in explaining long-term forest change in Austria. Trade-offs of forest transitions resulting from problem shifts to these activities warrant further scrutiny in addition to the currently more commonly-addressed problem shifts related to land displacement and yield increase.

Our integrated approach lays the ground for a new typology of forest transitions pathways, discerned not by their economic or political context, but by major socio-ecological, biophysical enabling conditions. Our results underscore that biomass is a severely limited resource. Ensuring sustainable wood provision while at the same time effectively mitigating climate change will only be possible through transformative changes in energy and food systems which diverge from past industrialization trajectories of increasing production and consumption. In other words, the future climate-change mitigation effect of forest transitions will depend on the limitation of emissions from their enabling conditions outside the forest sector. Assessing these enabling conditions requires research and policy integration beyond sectoral foci on national land and energy systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simone Gingrich: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Visualization, Funding acquisition. **Christian Lauk:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft. **Fridolin Krausmann:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Karl-Heinz Erb:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Julia Le Noë:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105624](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105624).

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